

Ultra-Wideband Temperature Dependent Dielectric Spectroscopy of Porcine Muscle in the Microwave Frequency Range

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Abstract— The knowledge of dielectric properties of tissue is a crucial factor to develop new systems for medical applications. In the field of thermotherapy (e.g. hyperthermia) the frequency and temperature dependency of these properties are of high importance. To this end, we investigate the dielectric properties of porcine muscle in the temperature range between 30 °C and 50 °C from 0.5 GHz to 7 GHz. Based on these data we determine temperature coefficients of the relative permittivity and effective conductivity. In both cases, the results show a weak temperature dependency and a change of sign of the temperature coefficients in the specified frequency range.

Keywords— dielectric spectroscopy, temperature dependent properties of muscle, M-sequence, ultra-wideband, open-ended coaxial probe

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyperthermia offers a nontoxic approach to support oncological treatments (e.g. chemotherapy or radiotherapy) by heating up the tumorous tissue to a temperature between 41 °C and 45 °C [1]. In order to guarantee the patient safety it is crucial that the temperature does not exceed the specified limit and the surrounding healthy tissue should not be affected by the heating process. Furthermore, the knowledge of the temperature distribution within the treated area can be used to control the power of the applicator system. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor the temperature during the treatment. Commonly, invasive optical catheters are used to control the temperature during hyperthermia treatment, but this method is painful to the patient and the spatial resolution is limited to a single point per probe. Nowadays promising alternative methods exist, such as magnetic resonance imaging, ultrasound or microwave temperature monitoring, to obtain the temperature distribution non-invasively.

In our previous feasibility studies [2], [3], we presented an approach for non-invasive differential temperature measurements by means of UWB microwaves. The method is based on the temperature dependent dielectric properties of biological tissue. In the microwave frequency range, the permittivity is mainly characterized by the water content of tissue. Due to the fact that the permittivity of water decreases

with increasing temperature, a selective heating of the target area leads to a decreasing permittivity of high water content tissue. This results in a changing scattering behavior of an incident electromagnetic wave which can be recorded by UWB radar technology. To determine the measured differences corresponding to the temperature change inside of the body it is necessary to obtain knowledge about the temperature dependent dielectric properties of tissue. A variety of studies considering the complex permittivity of tissue exists, but most of them only investigated the dielectric properties at a constant temperature [4]. The temperature dependency over a wide frequency range is considered by only a few studies [5]. Further studies investigated the temperature dependency at single frequencies for different tissues. A review can be found in Rossmann and Haemmerich [6].

The purpose of this contribution is to investigate the temperature dependent dielectric properties of porcine muscle tissue in a temperature range between 30 °C and 50 °C from 0.5 GHz to 7 GHz.

Fig. 1. Measurement setup for UWB spectroscopy of porcine muscle using an UWB M-sequence NWA connected to the coaxial probe (performance probe, Keysight Technologies). A temperature probe connected to the high precision thermometer (GMH 3750, GHM Messtechnik GmbH) records the temperature. Both, UWB radar signals and temperature are stored by a custom developed software in parallel.

Fig. 2. (a) Relative permittivity and (b) effective conductivity of muscle at 37°C for different storage times. Each curve shows the dielectric properties of one sample, whereby curves of the same color indicate samples of the same animal. (c) Mean relative permittivity and (d) mean effective conductivity of porcine muscle averaged over twelve samples at 37°C with the corresponding standard deviation. Black curves show the dielectric properties of muscle reported by Gabriel (ovine).

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The measurements of dielectric properties were performed by means of a coaxial probe (N1501A performance probe, Keysight Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) connected to an UWB M-sequence network analyzer developed at the Technische Universität Ilmenau. Further details of the working principle of the NWA can be found in [7], [8]. Fig. 1 shows the measurement setup which is almost identical to the setup presented in [9]. The temperature probe was connected to a high precision thermometer (GMH 3750, GHM Messtechnik GmbH).

The porcine muscle tissues were obtained from a local slaughter house. The measurements started between two and 60 hours after tissue examination, whereby the samples were stored in a fridge immediately after excision. The muscle samples had a cylindrical shape with a diameter of 6 cm and a height of 1 cm. They were wrapped in plastic foil with two holes on the upper surface to ensure a direct contact of the measurement probes with the tissue. The samples were placed in a water bath and the water temperature was controlled by a heating plate.

The dielectric properties are characterized in terms of the

complex relative permittivity

$$\underline{\varepsilon}(\omega, \vartheta) = \varepsilon'(\omega, \vartheta) - i\varepsilon''(\omega, \vartheta) \quad (1)$$

and the effective conductivity

$$\sigma(\omega, \vartheta) = \omega\varepsilon_0\varepsilon''(\omega, \vartheta) \quad (2)$$

where the real part ε' represents the relative permittivity, the imaginary part ε'' the relative dielectric loss, ε_0 the permittivity of free space, $\omega = 2\pi f$ the angular frequency and ϑ the temperature.

III. RESULTS

A. Dielectric properties at constant temperature

Fig. 2(a) and (b) show exemplarily the relative permittivity and the effective conductivity of eight porcine muscle samples from three animals for different storage times. Curves of the same color indicate samples corresponding to one animal. As it is evident from the plots, there is no trend between storage time and dielectric properties. From this it can be concluded that the inter-individual differences of tissue are higher than the influence of the storage time. Due to this finding we calculate the dielectric properties of tissue by averaging the results of different samples independent of the storage time.

Fig. 2(c) and (d) depict the mean relative permittivity as well as

Fig. 3. (a) Mean relative permittivity and (b) mean effective conductivity averaged over twelve samples as a function of frequency for five different temperatures (c) mean relative permittivity and (d) mean effective conductivity as a function of temperature for three selective frequencies (e,f) Temperature coefficients of muscle computed according to eq. (4). Black circles indicate the temperature dependent coefficients presented by Duck [10].

the mean effective conductivity averaged over twelve samples with the corresponding standard deviation. Furthermore, the experimental data are fitted to a two pole Cole-Cole model corresponding to

$$\underline{\varepsilon}(\omega) = \varepsilon_{\infty} + \frac{\Delta\varepsilon_1}{1 + (i\omega\tau_1)^{1-\alpha_1}} + \frac{\Delta\varepsilon_2}{1 + (i\omega\tau_2)^{1-\alpha_2}} + \frac{\sigma_s}{i\omega\varepsilon_0} \quad (3)$$

where ε_{∞} represents the permittivity at very high frequencies, $\Delta\varepsilon_{1,2}$ are the dispersion amplitudes, $\tau_{1,2}$ the corresponding

relaxation times and σ_s the static conductivity. The parameters $\alpha_{1,2}$ are empirical distribution parameters describing the broadening of the dispersion and were set to 0.18.

We used the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm to fit the Cole-Cole parameter to the measured data, whereby the initial values for the calculation of ε_{∞} , $\Delta\varepsilon_{1,2}$, $\tau_{1,2}$ and σ_s were set to the data presented by Gabriel (see table 1).

The fitted curves (Fig 2(c) and (d)) determined by the Cole-Cole parameters (table 1) and eq. (3) are in good accordance with the data presented by Gabriel [11].

Table 1. Comparison of the Cole-Cole parameters for the first and second pole of our study and the data presented by Gabriel [11] at 37 °C.

	ϵ_∞	$\Delta\epsilon_1$	$\tau_1(ps)$	$\Delta\epsilon_2$	$\tau_2(ns)$	σ_s
this study	4.76	50.75	6.63	7000	309.25	0.525
Gabriel	4.00	50.00	7.23	7000	353.68	0.200

B. Temperature dependent dielectric properties

The measurements presented in Fig. 2 show a high standard deviation due to the inter-individual differences between the samples, but the measurements of the individual samples show almost the same temperature dependent changes of the dielectric properties, which is evident from the averaged curves as depicted in Fig. 3(a) and (b). Both, the relative permittivity as well as the effective conductivity has an intersection point at 6.5 GHz and 3 GHz, respectively, where the dielectric properties do not change with temperature. The permittivity decreases with increasing temperature below the cross-over point. This trend reverses for frequencies higher than 6.5 GHz. The conductivity rises with increasing temperature below the cross-over point, whereby this trend also reverses for frequencies higher than 3 GHz.

Fig. 3(c) and (d) illustrate exemplarily the relative permittivity and effective conductivity as a function of temperature for three single frequencies. The curves show nearly a linear dependence of the dielectric properties on the temperature. To compare our results with the data known from literature, we calculate the temperature coefficients

$$\frac{\Delta\epsilon'}{\epsilon'} \text{ in } (\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}) \text{ and } \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\sigma} \text{ in } (\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}) \quad (4)$$

which describe the variations of the dielectric properties divided by a reference value. In this study, the reference is chosen according to the dielectric properties at 30 °C. The results agree well with the frequency specific values presented by Duck [10].

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we investigated the influence of the storage time of ex-vivo porcine muscle on the dielectric properties. If fluid loss of the tissue is avoided, the storage time has no influence on the dielectric properties, because the changes of dielectric properties in the microwave frequency range are mainly influenced by tissue hydration as postulated by Lazebnik [5] as well as by Farrugia [12].

The measurements and the derived Cole-Cole parameters of muscle tissue at a constant temperature of 37 °C are in accordance to data reported in the literature.

Furthermore, we measured the temperature dependency of the relative permittivity and effective conductivity in the temperature range between 30 and 50 °C from 0.5 up to 7 GHz. The relative permittivity has the highest temperature sensitivity in the frequency range between 0.5 and 4 GHz, whereby the effective conductivity shows an intersection point in this range at 3 GHz. At this frequency no temperature dependent contrast of the imaginary part will be induced. These results are crucial to determine optimal working conditions (e.g. bandwidth) in

terms of the development of a clinical microwave temperature monitoring system.

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